

PURPOSE AND FORMS OF ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

Khudayberdiev Abdurashid Abdirasulovich

Academy of the Interior Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Associate Professor of the Department of Administrative Law, Doctor of
Philosophy in Law.

(PhD), Associate Professor

Ochilov Bokhodir Khudoyberdievich

Head of the Department of Educational Work of the penal colony
Enforcement No. 13 of the first regional zone of the Department of
Penal Enforcement under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan

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Annotation: The article focuses on the goals and forms of activities of the structure operating in the educational and upbringing direction of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Key words: Upbringing, education, conscience, patriotism, loyalty, national pride, collective upbringing.

The reforms being carried out in our country today are aimed at educating future internal affairs officers, qualified personnel with high spiritual and intellectual potential, meeting the demands of today. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of employees of internal affairs bodies" adopted on August 16, 2017 served as an important foundation for the implementation of this work. In particular, "...the improvement of the training of qualified, highly qualified legal personnel who meet international standards and are true devotees of their profession" is a specific requirement of the time.

Today, our country is implementing deep and institutional reforms to bring the field of higher education to the level of developed countries around the world. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Develop the Higher Education System" of April 20, 2017, adopted in this direction, clearly defines the goal of fundamentally improving the higher education system, fundamentally revising the content of personnel training in accordance with the priority tasks of the country's socio-economic development, and creating the necessary conditions for training highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards.

Furthermore, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Enhancing the Effectiveness of State Youth Policy and Supporting the Activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" of July 5, 2017,[3] pays special attention to the training of qualified, knowledgeable and mature specialists, and states that "Youth is a solid legal foundation for the upbringing of a comprehensively developed, independent-thinking, capable of taking responsibility for the future of our country in accordance with the demands of today, initiative, mobilizing all their potential for the benefit of the people,

The fundamental basis of the reforms being carried out in the system is the training of qualified, professional, and most importantly, patriotic, honest and fair personnel for internal affairs bodies. This refers to the introduction of a new modern system of education, taking into account political, psychological, and professional aspects in the upbringing of a person

with professional qualifications and rapid adaptability in rapidly changing mass, informational, and technical processes.

Therefore, in educating young people in educational institutions, it is necessary to analyze the problems facing society as a person with good information and deep motivation, take measures to solve them, as well as educate a generation that assumes personal responsibility.

It should be noted that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" of September 16, 2016 served to further improve and increase the efficiency of the activities of the sphere. The norms of this law regulate that the activities of employees serving in internal affairs bodies are of paramount importance to the state and society, that the activities of employees in this sphere are directly related to ensuring the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, legality and the rule of law, peace and tranquility.

The organization of educational work should be carried out in accordance with the goal. Through this, the main features of the study of the cadet's personal characteristics and the conditions that directly affect the harmonious development of personality are identified, forms and methods of education are selected taking into account these functions, and all educational work is organized.

One of the requirements for organizing educational work in educational structures is its regular conduct. After all, systematicity can be strengthened not only through the planning of work, the regularity of educational activities, the use of means and methods of education through the repetition of pedagogical actions.

Group forms of organizing educational work also include legal awareness and legal education, group discussions, reports, recording in journals, and others.

In this case, group forms of organization of educational work are held in the form of general meetings, which include solemn encouragement, including publication in wall publications, awards, laying wreaths at military memorials, solemn swearing-in, issuance of certificates, state awards, badges, and announcement of gratitude.

The main content of organizing educational work in educational structures will consist of explaining the goals and objectives of youth preparation for service in internal affairs bodies and instilling and promoting the idea of serving the people.

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the direction of official activity of the internal affairs bodies:

- knowledge of the essence of legislation, state and government measures and requirements for the further activities of internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- the presence of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens;

- Knowledge of the system and structure of internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a strong belief in their high strength;

- the skills and abilities necessary for the successful acquisition of a particular specialty;
- having experience in a specific practical field (driving a car, motorcycle, firing a firearm, etc.).

The aforementioned abilities and qualities serve as the foundation for the performance of tasks in the field of training trainees and cadets in educational structures of educational institutions of internal affairs bodies, indicators of the formation of readiness to combat crime, as well as the organization of educational work and the search for means of its implementation.

The characteristics of the readiness of law enforcement agencies to serve the people in educating students and cadets of educational institutions are manifested in the following.

Preparing young people for the fight against crime is a long process that takes place throughout a person's life. Upbringing begins in the family and continues in school from elementary school. This process should be continued in the upbringing of trainees and cadets of educational institutions of internal affairs bodies.

The following tasks are set for the upbringing of trainees and cadets in the educational structures of educational institutions of the internal affairs bodies:

- raising the quality of educational and upbringing processes in accordance with world standards;

- the application of new teaching methods, modern pedagogical and information technologies;

- education and upbringing of young people in the spirit of knowledge of the national idea, universal values, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideas of independence, regular work with students;

- identification of able and talented young men and women and creation of conditions for their study abroad;

- training and increasing the capabilities of specialists of educational structures of educational institutions of the ministry of internal affairs to be able to compete with foreign specialists;

- providing the material and technical base with new literature, modern equipment and computer equipment, creating conditions for increasing the respect of teachers.

The following tasks are addressed through the implementation of educational work:

- the formation of a conscious attitude of employees towards the performance of official duties;

- improving the level of discipline, organization and compliance with the rule of law; development of patriotism.

One of the important components of the success of educational work in educational structures is the knowledge of the principles of educational work and the ability to apply their requirements in practice.

The principles of educational work represent an integral system and include:

- relying on the positive in the individual and the collective;

- collective and collective upbringing;

- unity of education and upbringing;

- respect for the individual and his personal dignity;

- individual and differentiated approach to upbringing;

the direct connection, unity, and consistency of subjects taught in the educational process with educational activities.

In educational structures, the most common and effective form of educational work in practice is individual conversation. Here, as a means of personal communication and educational action, the leader's lively speech, the ability to conduct a confidential, open conversation, are used. The conversation may have a different character, have different goals, and focus on different issues of official and personal life. It can be informative, motivational, or orientational.

Individual conversation, openly, without genuine discussion, requires knowledge of the inner driving forces of the student's behavior, the sources of their activity or the reasons for their passivity in service, the specifics of their perception of the world and their assessment of the environment.

A necessary condition for the success of the conversation is that the relationship between the leader and the subordinate should be based on goodwill, reputation, his moral purity, kindness, and respect for the youth.

It is necessary to support and encourage employees' aspirations for self-education, based on their active activities, in order to develop the necessary professional and moral qualities through self-education, self-development, self-analysis, and self-assessment in management.

Depending on the characteristics of the individual and the goals of educational influence, various methods of educational work should be used - persuasion, training, encouragement, coercion, and positive examples.

The method of persuasion, appealing to human knowledge, experience, and emotions, ensures the voluntary acceptance of ideas, their independent understanding, and their transformation into behavioral motives.

Incentives are a unique set of methods and means of moral and material incentives for employees of internal affairs bodies. Stimulation is a very delicate and powerful means of educating subordinates, and its use requires a serious and profound attitude from the educator. Using their right to encourage, the educator must take into account the individual characteristics of the individual and collective opinion, as well as choose appropriate conditions for celebrating the subordinate's actions. An employee with the ability to apply a set of incentive methods must always solve a number of problems:

Coercion refers to a system of means and methods of influencing employees who violate laws, orders, and moral norms in order to correct their actions and encourage them to fulfill their duties with good intentions.

Force means to force the will of an employee to perform it before the collective in the interests of solving the tasks facing the internal affairs body (unit).

In conclusion, it should be noted that every employee of the internal affairs body must be loyal to his people, his homeland, his duty, his service, be spiritually and morally mature, be a master of his craft, a public servant, and be highly educated.

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